

Supporting Information

Electrical Transport of Nb-Doped MoS₂ Homojunction P-N Diode: Investigating NDR and Avalanche Effect

Ehsan Elahi^{1#}, Umer Ahsan^{1#}, Muhammad Farooq Khan², Jamal Aziz³, Payal Chauhan¹, Paweł Piotr Michałowski⁴, Yuan Chen⁵, Goki Eda^{5,6,7}, Martin Loula⁸, Kalyan Jyoti Sarkar^{1*}, Zdenek Sofer^{1*}

¹*Department of Inorganic Chemistry, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague Technická 5, Prague 616628, Czech Republic*

²*Department of Electrical Engineering, Sejong University, 209 Neungdong-ro, Gwangjin-gu, Seoul, 05006, South Korea*

³*Chair of Smart Sensor Systems, University of Wuppertal, Wuppertal, Germany*

⁴*Lukasiewicz Research Network - Institute of Microelectronics and Photonics, Aleja Lotników 32/46, 02-668 Warsaw, Poland*

⁵*Department of Physics, National University of Singapore, 2 Science Drive 3, Singapore 117551, Singapore*

⁶*Department of Chemistry, National University of Singapore, 3 Science Drive 3, Singapore 117543, Singapore*

⁷*Centre for Advanced 2D Materials, National University of Singapore, Singapore 117546, Singapore*

⁸*Institute of Organic Chemistry and Biochemistry of the ASCR, v.v.i., Flemingovo nám. 2, 166 10 Prague, Czech Republic*

[#]*These two authors contributed equally*

Corresponding Authors (*): Kalyan Jyoti Sarkar: sarkark@vscht.cz ; Zdenek Sofer: Zdenek.Sofer@vscht.cz

The photoluminescence (PL) spectra of Nb-doped MoS₂ clearly demonstrate the thickness-dependent bandgap evolution. In the monolayer case (**Figure S1(g)**), a strong PL peak appears near 700 nm, corresponding to a direct bandgap of ≈ 1.78 eV. As the material thickness increases to the multilayer regime (**Figure S1(h)**), the PL peak shifts to around 900 nm, giving an effective bandgap of ≈ 1.38 eV, while the reduced emission intensity reflects the crossover toward an indirect bandgap. For the bulk-like sample (**Figure S1(i)**), the PL maximum is observed near 1029.2 nm, corresponding to ≈ 1.21 eV, which matches the reported indirect bandgap values for bulk MoS₂. This monotonic decrease in bandgap with increasing thickness is further influenced by Nb doping, which induces slight band renormalization and broadening of the emission spectra. These trends are in agreement with previous studies on the optical properties of MoS₂ across different thicknesses

Figure S1: (a) Optical image of Nb-doped MoS₂ transferred onto a holey SiN₃ TEM grid. (b,c) Additional large-area HAADF-STEM images of multilayer Nb-doped MoS₂ from different regions of the sample. (d) EDX spectrum. (e) EDX spectrum acquired from $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}^2$ region of the suspended sample. (f) Elemental composition of the sample

measured by SIMS. (g-i) PL spectra of Nb-doped MoS₂ flakes (monolayer, multilayer, bulk) showing thickness-dependent bandgap red-shift from ~1.78 to ~1.20 eV.

SIMS results

The elemental composition of individual samples was measured by SIMS at different depths (0.1 μm, 1 μm, 10 μm, and 100 μm). Each table presents data for a different crystal, highlighting depth-dependent variations.

Sample 1 (table-S1)

Element	0.1 μm	1 μm	10 μm	100 μm
Mo	32.6246 ± 0.0348	32.6068 ± 0.0346	32.6124 ± 0.0351	32.6590 ± 0.0300
Nb	0.4950 ± 0.0152	0.5650 ± 0.0180	0.5657 ± 0.0173	0.5645 ± 0.0118
S	64.7197 ± 0.0421	66.4900 ± 0.0442	66.3883 ± 0.0507	66.4333 ± 0.0348
O	1.8977 ± 0.0897	0.0012 ± 0.0004	0.0018 ± 0.0004	0.0017 ± 0.0004

Sample 2 (table-S2)

Element	0.1 μm	1 μm	10 μm	100 μm
Mo	32.6020 ± 0.0770	32.7350 ± 0.0670	32.5870 ± 0.0550	32.7010 ± 0.0550
Nb	0.4930 ± 0.0220	0.5720 ± 0.0370	0.5770 ± 0.0460	0.5570 ± 0.0170
S	63.5920 ± 0.0640	66.5210 ± 0.0730	66.3320 ± 0.0710	66.5250 ± 0.0550
O	2.9620 ± 0.1680	0.0011 ± 0.0007	0.0016 ± 0.0006	0.0025 ± 0.0008

Sample 3 (table-S3)

Element	0.1 μm	1 μm	10 μm	100 μm
Mo	32.5550 ± 0.0700	32.6920 ± 0.0970	32.5470 ± 0.0950	32.5570 ± 0.0780
Nb	0.5060 ± 0.0300	0.5470 ± 0.0350	0.5540 ± 0.0290	0.5540 ± 0.0270
S	65.3130 ± 0.0630	66.4140 ± 0.0660	66.3860 ± 0.0940	66.4250 ± 0.0670
O	1.0200 ± 0.1340	0.0015 ± 0.0006	0.0024 ± 0.0006	0.0007 ± 0.0005

Sample 4 (table-S4)

Element	0.1 μm	1 μm	10 μm	100 μm
Mo	32.7990 ± 0.0790	32.6360 ± 0.0960	32.7700 ± 0.0860	32.5520 ± 0.0540
Nb	0.4850 ± 0.0440	0.5690 ± 0.0480	0.5540 ± 0.0390	0.5680 ± 0.0220
S	65.2540 ± 0.0890	66.5350 ± 0.0890	66.4470 ± 0.0960	66.3500 ± 0.0580
O	1.2270 ± 0.1200	0.0025 ± 0.0006	0.0010 ± 0.0008	0.0018 ± 0.0006

Sample 5 (table-S5)

Element	0.1 μm	1 μm	10 μm	100 μm
Mo	32.5720 ± 0.0990	32.4940 ± 0.0580	32.5710 ± 0.0730	32.7800 ± 0.0600
Nb	0.5140 ± 0.0310	0.5660 ± 0.0480	0.5620 ± 0.0160	0.5480 ± 0.0330
S	64.1690 ± 0.0700	66.4210 ± 0.0710	66.4980 ± 0.0530	66.5200 ± 0.0520
O	2.4410 ± 0.1040	0.0019 ± 0.0007	0.0012 ± 0.0006	0.0024 ± 0.0007

X-Ray Diffraction

Figure S2: X-ray diffraction (XRD) of pristine MoS₂ and Nb-Doped MoS₂.

Stability of the device

Figure S3: (a) Optical image of the device after 2 months. (b) I-V curves of the p-n homojunction of Nb-doped MoS₂ as the function of V_g , after one week. (c) I-V curves of Nb:MoS₂ after two months.

Device-2

Figure S4: (a) The optical image of the fabricated device based on the homojunction of Nb-doped MoS₂. (b) I-V curves of the p-n homojunction of Nb-doped MoS₂ as the function of V_g . (c) Transfer curves of Nb: MoS₂. (d) Transfer curves in logarithmic scale.

Mobility and carrier concentration of Bulk Nb-doped MoS₂:

The carrier concentration value for pristine MoS₂ is 3.43x10¹⁴ atoms/cm³ and 6.84x10¹⁹ atoms/cm³ for Nb-doped with applied current I=1 mA.

No	Thickness (cm)	Magnetic Field (±mT)	Temperature (K)	Hall Voltage (mV)	Hall coefficient (cm ³ /C)	Bulk carriers concentration (/cm ³)	Sheet carriers concentration (/cm ²)	Hall Mobility (cm ² /V. s)	Resistivity (Ω.cm)	Conductivity (/Ω.cm)
1	0.117	100	300	2.50E-05	0.292527	2.14E+19	2.50E+18	2.840391	0.102988	9.709851
2	0.117	200	300	3.13E-05	0.182821	3.42E+19	4.00E+18	1.777339	0.102862	9.721739
3	0.117	300	300	0.000106251	0.414378	1.51E+19	1.76E+18	4.022516	0.103015	9.707351
4	0.117	400	300	3.12E-05	0.0914	6.84E+19	8.00E+18	6.289136	0.102796	9.728009
5	0.117	500	300	0.000125006	0.292514	2.14E+19	2.50E+18	6.838802	0.103041	9.704854

Table S6: The characteristics of Nb-doped MoS₂-based bulk crystal

Ideality factor calculation

The ideality factor was calculated for the forward-biased zone by fitting the logarithmic I-V characteristics to the Shockley diode equation [1, 2].

$$I_D = I_S \left[\exp\left(\frac{qV}{\eta k_B T}\right) - 1 \right]$$

Where I_D represents the diode current, I_S represents the reverse bias saturation current, V denotes the applied voltage, η symbolizes an ideality factor, T signifies temperature, q symbolizes electronic charge, and k_B indicates Boltzmann's constant. For applied voltages larger than $k_B T$ (e.g., > 0.1 V), the term "-1" in the preceding equation can be ignored.

$$\ln(I_D) = \ln(I_S) + \left(\frac{q}{\eta k_B T}\right) V$$

$$\eta = \frac{1}{\text{slope}} \left(\frac{q}{k_B T}\right)$$

$$\eta = \frac{1}{\text{slope}} \left(\frac{1.6 \times 10^{-19} \text{C}}{1.38 \times 10^{-23} \text{JK}^{-1} \times 300 \text{K}}\right)$$

Slope= 31.34

$$\eta = \frac{38.6}{31.34} = 1.23 \text{ at } V_g = -30\text{V}.$$

Figure S5: Ideality factor calculation at back gate voltage $V_g = -30$ V. (b) Gate-controlled band diagrams $V_g = -30$ V, illustrate the maximum rectification.

NDR Effect in Device-1

Figure S6: (a-i) Investigation of NDR effect in device-1 at different temperatures.

Photoresponse at different Wavelengths

Figure S7: (a-f) Photoresponse of the device-1 at different wavelengths (370, 405, 470, 530, 625, 740 nm).

Rise and decay time

Figure S8: (a) Rise time and (b) Decay time of device-1 at wavelength 625 nm.

References

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